

KERAMIK MATERIALLARNI TAYYORLASHDA SANOAT
CHIQUINDILARINI QO'SHISH BILAN UNING FIZIK-MEXANIK
XOSSALARINI YAXSHILASH.

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Annotatsiya: *Maqolada keramik materiallar tayyorlashda maxalliy gil tuproq tarkibiga sanoat chiqindisi xisoblanmish shisha kukunini qo'shish orqali tayyorlanayotgan materialning xossalarini yaxshilash ustida olib borilgan tajriba natijalari bayon qilingan. Xususan, tajribada sinalayotgan namunaga 30 % shisha kukuni qo'shilganda, tayyorlangan namunaning egilishga va siqilishga bo'lgan mustaxkamligi bir necha marta ortganligi aniqlangan. Shisha chiqindilaridan keramik buyumlar tayyorlashda foydalanish maxsulot xossalarini yaxshilash bilan birga, chiqindilarni qayta ishlash orqali ekologiyani saqlashga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *keramik materiallar, shisha kukuni, normal quyuklik, sanoat chiqindisi, gil tuproq, mufel pechi, gidravlik press, GOST, elektron tarozi, marka, kashkarov bolgasi.*

УЛУЧШЕНИЕ ЕГО ФИЗИКО-МЕХАНИЧЕСКИХ СВОЙСТВ С
ДОБАВЛЕНИЕМ ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ОТХОДОВ ПРИ ПОЛУЧЕНИИ
КЕРАМИЧЕСКИХ МАТЕРИАЛОВ.

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Аннотация: В статье описаны результаты эксперимента по улучшению свойств материала, полученного путем добавления промышленного безотходного стеклянного порошка в состав местной глинистой глины при приготовлении керамических материалов. В частности, когда к испытываемому в эксперименте образцу добавляли 30% стеклянного порошка, было обнаружено, что прочность подготовленного образца на изгиб и сжатие увеличилась в несколько раз. Использование отходов стекла при приготовлении керамических изделий, помимо улучшения свойств изделий, оказывает положительное влияние на сохранение экологии за счет переработки отходов производства.

Ключевые слова: керамический материал, стеклянный порошок, нормальная толщина, промышленные отходы, глинистая глина, муфельная печь, гидравлический пресс, ГОСТ, электронные весы, марка, молоток кашкаров.

IMPROVING ITS PHYSICAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES WITH THE ADDITION OF INDUSTRIAL WASTE IN THE PRODUCTION OF CERAMIC MATERIALS.

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Annotation: The article describes the results of an experiment to improve the properties of a material obtained by adding industrial waste-free glass powder to the composition of local clay in the preparation of ceramic materials. In particular, when 30% of glass powder was added to the sample tested in the experiment, it was found that the bending and compressive strength of the prepared sample increased several times. The use of glass waste in the preparation of ceramic products, in addition to improving the properties

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of products, has a positive impact on the preservation of the environment through the processing of production waste.

Key words: ceramic material, glass powder, normal thickness, industrial waste, clay clay, muffle furnace, hydraulic press, GOST, electronic scales, brand, hammer kashkarov.

One of the main global problems facing all countries of the world is the problem of reduction and processing of industrial waste. As a result of the increase in the amount of industrial waste, landfills are being used year after year. As a result of the negative impact of waste on nature, the environment is deteriorating more and more, and during the seasons of precipitation, groundwater pollution, and the development of energy-efficient building materials, the processing of industrial wastewater is one of the urgent problems we face.

This problem remains relevant despite the fact that measures have been taken to reduce the amount of products that can be produced by processing industrial waste, non-recyclable waste. Over time, one of the decomposed waste that does not aggravate the condition of the bonds is various glass products. An empty bottle can be recycled in a glassware factory with up to a certain percentage added. However, it is not possible to process empty bottles with a full scan. One of the reasons for this is the low cost of quartz sand and other components in the extraction of glass, another reason is the cost of the processes of separating, cleaning, crushing and packaging bottles from waste, as well as a lot of time wasted.

To solve the problem of glass waste, samples were prepared and tested in the laboratory of the Department of "Special Sciences" of the Yangiyer branch of the Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology with the addition of glass waste powder to clay soil, and results were obtained. In particular, clay soil was taken from the territory of the village of Dzhulangar, Yangiabad district, Jizzakh region, and a drinking bottle was chosen for bottle waste.

- a) electronic scales and suspension soil
- b) crushed glass
- c) hammer kashkarov.

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The soil and glass selected for the sample were sifted through a crushing sieve. In the composition of the soil prepared for the samples, different percentages of glass powder were added for each sample, and the layer was poured into molds of normal thickness measuring 40x40x160 mm. When the samples lost moisture, they were baked in a muffle furnace at a temperature of 950-1000 degrees (in a village oven). It was found that these samples, which have the appearance of a ceramic object, are self-sufficient for bending and compacting in the equipment invented by kafedra, in the glikavlik press, which is available in the laboratory.

1) with 25-30% samples

2) hydraulic press

3) muffle furnace

Based on the recorded strength indicators, a table was compiled. According to the results obtained, it was found that the addition of 30% glass powder to clay soil gives several times more strength compared to pure samples. In particular, the bending strength of a clean specimen is 23.5 MPa, and the compressive strength is 87 MPa; The bending strength of the sample with 30% glass powder was 70 MPa, and the compressive strength was 250 MPa.

Thus, the addition of glass waste fragments in the production of ceramic materials can be of great service to the environment by improving product properties, conserving existing soil resources, and eliminating industrial waste.

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